

CHARACTERISTICS AND THEIR ANALYSIS OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' LINGUISTIC AND LANGUAGE COMPONENTS BY WORD GROUPS IN PRIMARY CLASS MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

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Abstract. *In the classes of mother tongue and reading literacy of the primary grade, there are comments based on theoretical and practical experiences about the features of formation of linguistic and language components of students, signs and learning analysis. attention is also paid to the issue of development, and the role of primary education is discussed in it.*

Keywords: *language and linguistic component, primary education, educational content, cognitive activity, linguistic personality.*

The development features of modern Uzbek society lead to the emergence of new approaches to the content and forms of education. It also affects the formation of other ideas about the goals and tasks of education. Changes in the content of education, which affect various areas of the educational process, are also related to the technological aspects of education, creating different educational models and almost all special educational courses. , including the need to update the mother tongue and reading literacy course. Not only the problems of choosing the content and organizing the process of acquiring knowledge about the native language, but also the development of students' ability to be cognitively active, as well as taking into account objective processes due to the internal laws of the development of the native language, the language itself, the formation of the child as linguistic personality features remain relevant.

The purpose of education is formed according to the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The purpose of education in scientific literature is to create skills and qualifications for the correct, accurate and appropriate use of opportunities, to develop logical and creative thinking, to increase communicative literacy, to inculcate the national idea, to form oriental education, to define the individual. it is emphasized that it consists of spiritual enrichment. Based on the educational goal, students' communication culture is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written literacy, and developing logical thinking. On the basis of the educational goal, spiritual, ideological and refined education is given. In the process of language learning, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of the people.

Primary education deserves special attention in the process of forming a language personality. Because primary education lays the foundation for all-round development of children. This is where work begins on the development of speech culture and the formation of a conscious attitude. It is at this stage that more attention is paid to the language and issues of linguistic ability development, and the foundation for the future is laid.

Considering primary language education as a phenomenon that includes aspects that develop language, speech, personality, it is necessary to emphasize the connection between the student's language education and his development as a language personality. At the same time, a

linguistic person is understood as a set of abilities and characteristics of a person that determine the creation and perception of a speech work. In the process of implementing this relationship, the formation of language, linguistic and communicative competences of the student is of crucial importance.

The content of teaching the mother tongue at school comes from the tasks that our state has set before the school at the current stage of society's development. These tasks are multifaceted, and their fulfillment is aimed at developing the minds of students, giving them ideological-political, moral, aesthetic and labor education.

As a result of learning the mother tongue and reading literacy, the students will be able to express their thoughts grammatically correct, methodologically clear, meaningful, following the tone and write it correctly. Linguistic analysis carried out in primary classes is of great importance in successfully solving these tasks. Linguistic analysis is also given special importance in the elementary mother tongue and reading literacy program.

In the teaching of mother tongue and reading literacy, the main focus is on the formation of four language skills: reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking and writing, and grammatical literacy.

In the "Mother tongue and reading literacy" textbooks of elementary grades, in the methodical manuals created for teachers, there are no instructions on teaching students to linguistic analysis. The main task of primary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes is to develop students' speech. It is very important to master the language phenomena, to know their similarities and differences in the successful implementation of speaking activities.

Teaching is based on a communicative approach, that is, the communication function of the language is primary. Also, it is necessary to take into account the activity-oriented approach, the conscious approach, the discovery approach, and the critical approach. Consider students' creative thinking as one of the necessary factors for developing the level of independent thinking and speech, as the characteristics and signs of the formation of linguistic and language components of students in terms of word groups in elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes. can also be shown.

In the mother tongue and reading literacy classes conducted in the primary school, students acquire knowledge, skills, and appropriate knowledge from the departments of linguistics such as phonetics, lexicology, morphemes, word formation, word groups, and syntax. formation of skills is carried out based on the requirements of the program and textbooks. There are many tried-and-tested methods of checking and controlling the state of knowledge, skills and competences acquired by students from the above-mentioned sections and topics. Elementary school teachers have been using these methods effectively in their experience. But the work of teaching students to linguistic analysis is not only to correctly and truthfully determine the level of knowledge, skills, and qualifications acquired by primary school students in the subject of their native language, but also to train them to think independently and creatively, logically. forces to engage in mental activities such as thinking, differentiating existing language phenomena, summarizing, comparing, and grouping them, and as a result, it leads to the expansion of the child's worldview based on a critical look at the existing language phenomena, the formation of scientific observation and reasoning skills will come. That's why teaching students to linguistic analysis in mother tongue and reading literacy classes has an important socio-pedagogical value.

The problem of teaching students linguistic analysis in the process of mother tongue and reading literacy education is not new in the theory and methodology of language teaching. Teaching students to linguistic analysis has been thoroughly studied by Russian scientist A.V. Tekuchev, Uzbek scientists Y. Abdullaev, H. Gulomova, M. Mirmahmudova. However, in their work, teaching primary school students to linguistic analysis was not taken as a research object.

In their textbooks, T.Ashrapova, M.Odilova paid special attention to the topic of "Grammatical analysis and its types". They emphasize the importance of grammar analysis: "It is conducted in order to assess the extent to which students have mastered the knowledge of grammar and spelling," and they call attention to the importance of grammar analysis:

According to the content: phonetic, morphological, syntactic, mixed analysis;

By volume: full analysis, incomplete analysis;

According to the form: they are divided into such types as oral and written. Even in this textbook, there is no opinion about the consistency of grammar analysis in elementary grades, the use of didactic tools in analysis.

The analysis of the collected literature, a number of monographs and sources on the issue shows that there are different approaches to the interpretation of these terms in language didactics. Thus, in the methodology of teaching the mother tongue, the terms "linguistic" and "linguistic competence" are used synonymously or defined as limited and independent.

It seems appropriate to distinguish between linguistic and linguistic competence in the methodology of teaching mother tongue and reading literacy. The need for this comes from the fact that mastering the mother tongue includes, on the one hand, the mastering of language units and the rules of their formation, and on the other hand, knowledge of the language and its system. The essence of language competence, in our opinion, means "mastering the language system, mastering the language material".

Linguistic competence in the methodology of teaching the subject of the mother tongue includes knowledge of the basics of the subject, the conceptual basis of the course, a set of certain concepts (language units and categories: phoneme, grapheme, morpheme): phrase, sentence, sentence. vocabulary, lexical and grammatical language units, etc.

In the formation of linguistic competence, the recognition of language phenomena and the purposeful acquisition of methods of action that ensure their use in speech also play an important role.

Learning the language system is not an end in itself. In the process of formation of linguistic competence, it is important to develop the student's personality, cognitive culture, logical memory, self-evaluation and introspection skills. The task of educating the language personality and forming linguistic and language components in elementary school students by means of the science of mother tongue and reading literacy comes to the fore based on the cognitive function and cognitive importance of the language.

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